

METHODOLOGICAL TRAINING OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCIES OF PRIMARY SCHOOL TEACHERS AS A PEDAGOGICAL PROBLEM

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Abstract. Currently, one of the important areas of formation of professional competencies of primary school teachers is to increase readiness for the implementation of the national curriculum. It is teachers who should ensure that such an important task of an educational institution is solved when introducing a national curriculum as improving the pedagogical process and increasing the developmental effect of educational work. It should be noted that the managerial function of a teacher is so important in the teacher's awareness of it (which, we repeat, is not yet at a sufficient level in reality) that without it, the priority goal of his professional activity – the organization of the life of the student collective, the organization of the educational activities of each child loses its meaning.

Key words: formation, national curriculum, competence, pedagogical problem, improvement, primary classes.

МЕТОДИЧЕСКОЙ ПОДГОТОВКИ ПРОФЕССИОНАЛЬНЫХ КОМПЕТЕНЦИЙ У УЧИТЕЛЕЙ НАЧАЛЬНЫХ КЛАССОВ КАК ПЕДАГОГИЧЕСКАЯ ПРОБЛЕМА

Аннотация. В настоящее время одним из важных направлений формирования профессиональных компетенций учителей начальных классов является повышение готовности к внедрению национальной учебной программой. Именно педагоги должны обеспечить решение такой важной задачей образовательного учреждения при введении национальной учебной программой как совершенствование педагогического процесса и повышение развивающего эффекта образовательной работы. Необходимо отметить, что управленческая функция учителя настолько важна в осознании ее самим педагогом (чего, повторяем, пока нет в реальности на достаточном уровне), что без этого утрачивает смысл приоритетная цель его профессиональной деятельности – организация жизнедеятельности ученического коллектива, организация учебной деятельности каждого ребёнка.

Ключевые слова: формирования, национальной учебной программа, компетенция, педагогическая проблема, повышения, начальных классов.

INTRODUCTION

On measures to improve the quality of education and the development of scientific research in the field of mathematics.

Mathematics has been identified as one of the priority areas for the development of science in our country in 2020. Over the past period, a number of systematic works have been carried out aimed at raising mathematical science to a qualitatively new level:

firstly, the necessary conditions have been created for inviting our compatriots - mathematicians working in advanced scientific centers, and conducting international scientific research;

secondly, a system has been introduced to stimulate the work of young people who have won international subject Olympiads, as well as their teachers and mentors;

Thirdly, in order to ensure the mutual integration of higher education and scientific research, a new modern building of the V.I. Romanovsky Institute of Mathematics of the Academy of Sciences (hereinafter — the Institute) has been built on campus. Professional competence is considered as a phenomenon of gradual professionalization of the future teacher. When forming a system of pre-profile and profile training, it is necessary to take into account the experience of existing teachers in order to develop ethnographic competence. It is important to develop a system of methods for studying this issue, one of the most important elements of which can be a program of specialized training of students[1].

Based on the goals, objectives, hypothesis of the study and taking into account the results of the ascertaining experiment, the goals and methodology of the program development were determined in order to form professional competencies.

Competence is the result of education, expressed in a person's readiness to solve certain tasks of professional and non-professional activities based on the use of internal and external resources.

This is due to the fact that today there are a number of serious problems in regional institutes of retraining and advanced training, where the scientific and pedagogical potential and the educational process do not meet modern requirements. In addition, experts note, teachers practically do not carry out research activities, a system of external evaluation of their activities has not been developed[1].

METHOD AND METHODOLOGY

Despite the fact that when analyzing the types and structure of professional competencies in research, components of a very different nature are distinguished, most researchers (A.K. Bondarenko, A.P. Egorshin, etc.) note that competence is an integrative education. The views of various authors on the achievement of integrative professional competence can be reduced to three positions: according to the first point of view (I.A. Zimnaya, A.I. Novikov, etc.), it is necessary to identify the "core" of competence, designated as transferable, key skills that are non-objective, multifunctional, interdisciplinary.

The second position (S.G. Vershlovsky, T.M. Sorokina, etc.) reflects the integrative essence of the ACC on the basis of the structure of activity generally accepted in psychology, in the unity of the joint action of the motivational-orientation, executive, control and evaluation links of pedagogical work. The third position (H.A. Aminov, M.N. Karapetova, etc.) is to search for an additional system-forming factor of the structure of professional competence, which will create stable links between the elements[4].

The assessment of the professional activity of an elementary school teacher is ambiguous, for example, it can be evaluated from the perspective of various approaches:

The teacher is a modern specialist in the field of education. When viewed from this point of view, the teacher's personality includes two components – competence. An elementary school teacher is a teacher and educator of primary school children. A teacher is a carrier of professional pedagogical culture as an integrative personal professionally significant education, including five components presented in Table 1:

Table 1 - Components of the pedagogical culture system of the future primary school teacher.

Components of pedagogical culture.	Characteristics of the teacher's activity.
Communication component	Openness to communication and cooperation with students in the classroom and outside of school hours.
Constructive component	Organization of students' activities and their own professional activities.
Perceptual component	The ability to understand the emotional state and motives of the pupil's behavior, the ability to empathize (empathy).
Innovative component	The need for innovation, the renewal of professional experience, pedagogical search.
Reflexive component	Awareness of one's professional activity as the main sphere of one's personal self-determination, self-assessment of one's professional development.

Having analyzed the quality of the implementation of the management function of the educational process by future primary school teachers, it can be concluded that some successfully cope with this function and many of them switch to self-management (self-control), while others experience significant difficulties:

- in the combination of pedagogical tasks and the selection of relevant relevant educational, educational and developmental techniques and technologies, management of these processes;
- in an attempt to overcome the constantly felt shortage of personal time;
- in understanding the purpose of their professional activity, its compliance with personal needs and interests;
- in mastering the ways of self-regulation of mental states during the working day, after it, ways of regulating the mental states of students;
- in independent and timely decision-making (in the choice of goal-oriented and unambiguous, situational or perspective priorities), etc.

It should be noted that the managerial function of a teacher is so important in the teacher's awareness of it (which, we repeat, is not yet at a sufficient level in reality) that without it, the priority goal of his professional activity – the organization of the life of the student collective, the organization of the educational activities of each child loses its meaning.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The containment of some motives of activity and the activation of others (aiming at overcoming contradictions and difficulties) is the moment of controlling the will of the pupil, his emotional state. At the same time? the teacher himself is in a situation of constant stress (a huge set of volitional efforts)? and therefore he must be able to remove it both at home and in children (to manage the states of the muscular system of the body).

The ability to self-manage, for example, mental states and behavior, which allows optimal action in complex pedagogical situations (simple situations need less management), in psychology is called the ability of a teacher to self-regulation.

A teacher working with a group of students should be well aware of the formative role of the family and the dependence of this role on the value orientations of its members. Possession of such information allows you to anticipate how family relationships can affect the personal development of a child, his character, behavioral reactions. The interaction of the teacher with parents has a serious impact on the younger student during the adaptation period.

The interaction is also conditioned by the social requirements of society, which increasingly require full-fledged cooperation of the teacher with the family.

For the formation of cooperation between adults and children, it is important to represent the collective as a whole, as a large family that unites and lives interestingly if the joint activities of teachers, parents, and children are organized.

Psychological and pedagogical, regulatory and reflexive competencies are general professional, i.e. necessary for all teachers[7].

Subject and methodological competencies belong to the category of special competencies, they ensure the fulfillment of specific professional duties that are characteristic of a primary school teacher and allow him to distinguish from other teachers.

The listed competencies are closely interrelated, forming a complex structure, and their content represents the requirements for the professional activity of an elementary school teacher.

Table 2 - The main professional pedagogical competencies of the future primary school teacher

Competencies	Characteristics of competencies
Personal.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> active in protecting the interests of students; - commitment to the profession; - ability to make decisions independently; - orientation towards goal-setting and goal-attainment; - mental balance; - humanity; - versatility of personality; - pedagogical reflection; - pedagogical culture
Psychological and pedagogical.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - knowledge: methodological, theoretical, methodical, technological; - skills: informational, organizational, communicative, pedagogical techniques, applied; - subject competencies
Subject-creative.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - independent thinking and creative approach in solving pedagogical tasks; - creating situations that contribute to the motivation of students;

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - encouraging students to be creative; - the use of non-traditional methods, methods and techniques in teaching; - conducting experimental work; - research activities
Methodical.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - goal setting and planning of pedagogical activity; - self-control; - self-regulation of moral-volitional and other mental states; - effective management of your own time; - independent and timely decision-making; - designing, designing and implementing an effective educational process; - methods of hidden control of students' consciousness

Thus, a professional as an integral person must possess a set of significant professional and pedagogical qualities that allow him to most effectively implement the goals and objectives of his professional activity.

Being practice-oriented, the training of primary school teachers is complete. Thus, a graduate of a pedagogical college or university should exercise his professional functions at the master level.

DISCUSSION

For modern society, along with the growing processes of globalization and modernization, there is also an obvious tendency towards national and cultural identification, the desire of peoples to preserve their ethnic identity. World science interprets this phenomenon as an ethnic revival, putting forward new requirements for education.

Education that does not take into account the peculiarities of ethnic identity cannot be modern, therefore, educational work with the younger generation should be aimed at the formation of a unique lifestyle of the individual.

Educational activity requires a specialist to have broad and deep knowledge in various fields. This is especially true for an elementary school teacher who teaches students a number of different scientific disciplines. Consequently, his general knowledge should revolve in the field of linguistics, literature, mathematics, natural science, history, fine arts, music.

At the same time, it means not only possession of the content of the discipline, but also a broad outlook that allows for a deep analysis of various aspects of the surrounding reality. So, the teacher needs knowledge about cultural and historical objects and traditions of his city, region, he must be guided by the cultural and historical features of the peoples inhabiting the region, be aware of cultural events.

Thus, it is necessary to distinguish three indicators of professional competencies of teachers according to the general cultural criterion:

- general education and erudition;

- updating awareness in the field of cultural innovations;
- formed speech culture.

The content of pedagogical education is defined as a means of developing linguistic, professional, technological and other competencies that represent the modern model of professional activity of primary school teachers[8-9].

The programs of training seminars to improve the qualifications of primary school teachers are designed on the principles of consistency and integration of research, educational, projective, practice-oriented activities that meet the current state of today's primary school and the processes of modernization of the education system in Uzbekistan as a whole and in the region in particular.

In the postgraduate professional education of primary school teachers, it is necessary to take into account the need of teachers themselves for flexible and mobile education.

Multilevel education provides them with the opportunity to learn not only the cultural and historical traditions and values of the peoples living in the individual republics of the, but also to assimilate the world experience of teaching and raising children, universal values that unite teachers into a single professional community.

The acquired knowledge and experience within the framework of regional peculiarities can act as a certain limiter in the teacher's activity, and the learned norms and values do not become landmarks in a changing world and are themselves subject to reassessment. In this regard, it is necessary to revise the content of pedagogical education in the system of multilevel training of primary school teachers based on the integration of world experience, world values and regional characteristics.

Due to the fact that the cultural foundations of education determine the multicultural environment of education and personal development, it is necessary to train primary school teachers of a new type who can interact with culture, master culture, act as a carrier of values, a model of behavior of a certain culture and create a new culture of communication of life in a professional environment and in the system of teacher-student relations[12].

Pedagogical activity is defined not only as a way of self-expression and self-realization, but, above all, as a way of an individual's active existence. For a primary school teacher, his active existence is associated with the values of the teacher, his competencies, which are aimed at the formation of the competencies and values of his student. The teacher is always oriented in his activity to another person. He asserts the value of any of his students.

This shows the deep meaning of pedagogical activity and the humane value of global education. The development of the value orientations of a modern teacher in a multi-level education is associated with the fact that in the course of his activity it is assumed not only interaction with the student as a subject of activity, but also the impact on the behavior of his "Honored Interlocutor" - the student.

In this case, the teacher should be guided in behavior by value orientations "as the grounds for evaluating objects realized by the subject" (M.S. Kagan)..

Since the teacher, according to V.A. Slastenin, acts as "... an active subject who implements his way of life in the process of professional activity, as a carrier of pedagogical consciousness," his training should be aimed at mastering competencies that allow him to synthesize the values of different cultures, find common meanings and meanings in linguistic and cultural diversity.

CONCLUSION

Due to the fact that the state is a multinational state, the modernization of education is determined by a system-forming factor and is aimed at updating the content of pedagogical education, which is determined by the means of developing creative abilities, independence and the desire for self-education.

Since it is this aspect of pedagogical activity that is most relevant today.

In our study, the concept of "professional competence" is presented as a dynamic aspect of the professional training of a future teacher, a characteristic of the course and prospects of his professional growth, professional changes, both motivational and activity.

Thus, the category of "professional competence" is considered as a collective concept that defines the uniqueness of the teacher's personality as a teacher-educator and child psychologist.

It is based on the teacher's conceptual awareness of his pedagogical capabilities, the characteristics of the children's group, the prospects for its development of the originality of society (actual characteristics of social phenomena, the characteristics of the parent group, etc.).

Such conceptual awareness determines the professional flexibility of the teacher in the selection of pedagogical technologies, techniques that allow to successfully realize the main goal – to create conditions for the positive development of the student's personality.

In the study, the concept of professional competence is interpreted as a dynamic, procedural side of his professional training, a characteristic of professional growth, professional changes, both motivational and activity.

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